

A Study on Academic Motivation among Secondary School Students of Haridwar District

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Abstract

Academic motivation is the aim and tenacity which is associated with development of academics of the students. Academic motivation is also needed for better academic performance. If the child does not feel well motivated, then it hampers their academic growth. Number of times it is seen that students are being humiliated for their poor academic performance in front of all. This leads to not their upliftment but more of their downfall as they feel demotivated. This leads to a problematic situation. It is the role of every educator to guide and keep their students motivated all the time. The more a child feels motivated the better he/she performs. Academic motivation is always needed at all the stages of academic growth. Academic motivation of Secondary school students is significantly and positively related with their academic achievement. Hence, it is the duty of the educator to motivate in different manners their Secondary school students while conducting the class. The present study aims to examine Academic Motivation among students of Secondary school with respect to their gender, locality and type of school. The tool used by the investigator is Academic Motivation Inventory prepared and standardized by Prof. K.S. Misra. The study compromised a sample of 60 secondary school students of Grade IX from district Haridwar, Uttarakhand. The study revealed that Academic Motivation can lead to effective classroom environment.

Keywords

Academic Motivation, Secondary School Students, Gender, Locality, Type of School.

Introduction

Academic Motivation is a type of strong force to motivate students to learn and it is the essential need to shine in academic activities and by nature, it is multidimensional concept (Dhall, 2014). It is the casual factor for behaviour that is highly associated with activities and success of students and it includes lot of efforts, smooth management of academic activities and continuous efforts to attain their educational goals and level of persistent of students (Usher and Morris, 2012). Academic motivation showcase their inquisitives, rigour and progress towards achieving particular goal in their academics. Academic motivation is the outcome of a process due to internal or external factors. It is highly essential for involving of students in their academic work and deciding quantum of learning and analyzing performance and exposure to information and facets (Brouse et al 2010) and it is the inclination, hard work and determination associated with achievement in academics of students (Guiffrida et al 2013). Academic motivation is an important process within which starts and continues with activities for the sole objective of attaining academic goals (Ekeh and Njoku, 2014). It is also responsible for guiding behaviour and outlook of students for achieving their academic goals. It increases their energies and hard work and also improves their cognitive growth that leads to improving their achievement in academically. Students who are academically strong are also seen to be highly motivated academically and they are learning ample number of things and hold more knowledge and skills (Driscoll, 2005). They are the ones for transferring learning activities to new circumstances (Pugh and Bergin, 2006). Academic motivation is improvising success of students in their academic activities and also reduce failures in their academics which significantly affects the performance of students in the classrooms (Reynolds and Weigand, 2010). Academic motivation plays a crucial role for effective learning and achieving higher degree of performance of Secondary school students in their academics. Hence, an attempt is made to study academic motivation among Secondary school students.

Need of The Study

Academic motivation is important for the overall growth of a child. If not practiced in the classrooms from the early stage then it is one thing that might act as an obstacle in having a healthy classroom environment. The need of this study is to find out about the importance of academic motivation of secondary school students on the basis of their gender, locality as well as type of school.

Statement of The Problem

A Study on Academic Motivation among Secondary School Students of Haridwar District.

Aim of study

1. To study the academic motivation among Secondary school students with regard to their gender.
2. To study the academic motivation among Secondary school students with regard to the locality of school.
3. To study the academic motivation among Secondary school students with regard to the type of school.

Review of Literature

Siti, Sara and Mohd Ariff et al (2022) found that college students had higher degree of academic motivation and difference amid gender of college students and academic motivation was significant. Academic motivation had positive and significant relation with self-efficacy of college students.

Golder, J. (2021) conducted a study in the higher secondary school of West Bengal and found no difference in their psychological well-being or self-confidence. There is also a relationship between general mental health and academic motivation of secondary school children.

Munanu, N.R. et al., (2021) established that the ones who have good mental health exhibit more extrinsic orientation than intrinsic motivation.

Turhan, N.S. (2020) in his study in Turkey signified that the academic motivation gets affected based on gender.

Bugler, M. F. et al. (2019) concluded that after a thorough study on 384 boys and 366 girls that through a questionnaire that girls get highly motivated academically if paid proper attention and given guidance whereas for boys it was poor.

Sunita (2018) did her research work on 400 adolescents of Jhajhar and Dadri district of Haryana and showed prominent difference on the well-being of the adolescents. It was seen that the general well-being has an impact on the academic achievement and motivation of students. Its stated that if there is healthy school environment then the students will be more motivated and grow academically.

Mallick, K.S. et al. (2017) in his research carried out on 700 students of grade IX of both genders showed a good amount of difference in the academic motivation based on their gender. This difference was found mainly on the basis of their sex and not on the area of their residing as children of rural areas were seen to perform better in exam. Girls have been showing more academic motivation than boys.

Suhag, A. K. et al. (2016) collected 60 samples of 30 boys and 30 girls each from different schools of Khairpur Mir's. They concluded that to keep academically motivated is the new key of students. Only a well-motivated team of students can lead to a cognitively well-balanced group of academically smart students. The gender does not make much of a difference there.

Methodology In the present study, Descriptive Survey Method (Quantitative data collection method) was used to collect data about the investigation.

Variables of the Study

The variables in the present study are -

1. Dependent variables: Academic Motivation
2. Independent variables: Gender, Locality and Type of School

Sampling

A sample of 60 (30 boys and 30 girls) secondary school students has been drawn from the population of the students of IX standard from the district Haridwar, State Uttarakhand. The sample was drawn through Purposive Sampling Technique. The stratification has been based on their gender, living areas such as rural and urban as well as Type of school like Government and Private.

Tools Used Academic Motivation Inventory prepared and standardized by Professor K.S. Misra.

Statistics Used in the Study

In the present study, two types of statistical measures used such as Descriptive and Inferential statistics i.e. Mean, Standard Deviation (S.D.), and t-test have used.

Analysis

The collected data were analyzed with descriptive and inferential statistical techniques and interpreted.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the academic motivation among Secondary school students with regard to their gender

Table-1: Summary Table of Gender Wise t-value in Academic Motivation of Secondary Students

Variable	Gender	N	MEAN	S.D	df	t-value	Level of Significance
Academic Motivation	Boys	30	146	10.64	58	3.75	0.001
	Girls	30	160	17.05			

It is clear from the Table -1 that the calculated t-value is 3.75. This implied that the mean value for gender of secondary school students indicates that girls of secondary school students (M=160) have higher level of Academic Motivation than boys of Secondary school students (M=146). The t-value of 3.75 is revealing that significant difference exists amid gender of Secondary school students and their academic motivation in 1% level. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Fig 1: Graphical Representation of comparison of Mean & S.D in Academic Motivation of Boys and Girls Secondary School Students

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in academic motivation among high school students with regard to the locality of school

Table- 2: Summary Table of Location Wise t-value of Academic Motivation of Secondary Students

VARIABLE	Demographic Location	N	MEAN	S.D	df	t-value	Level of Significance
Academic Motivation	Rural	20	163.95	13.3	58	4.29	0.001
	Urban	40	147.7	14.05			

It is clear from the Table -2 that the calculated t-value is 4.29. The mean value for locality of school of Secondary school students indicates that Secondary school students studying in schools located in rural area (M=163.95) have higher level of Academic Motivation than urban area (M=147.7). The t-value of 4.29 is revealing that significant difference exists amid locality of school of high school students and their academic motivation in 1% level. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Fig 2: Graphical Representation of comparison of Mean & S.D in Academic Motivation of Rural and Urban Secondary School Students

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in academic motivation among Secondary school students with regard to the type of school

Table- 3: Summary Table of kind of school Wise t-value of Academic Motivation of Secondary Students

VARIABLE	STREAM	N	MEAN	S.D.	df	t-value	Level of Significance
Academic Motivation	Government	25	158.36	16.64	58	2.26	0.001
	Private	35	149.38	14			

It is clear from the Table -3 that the calculated t-value is 2.26. This implied that the mean value for type of school of Secondary school students indicates that secondary school students studying in government schools (M=158.36) have higher level of Academic Motivation than Private school (M=149.38) .The t-value of 2.26 revealing that significant difference exists amid type of school of high school students and their academic motivation in 1% level. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Fig 3: Graphical Representation of Comparison of Mean & S.D. in Academic Motivation of Govt. and Private Secondary School Students

Findings

1. There is significant difference in academic motivation of secondary school students with respect to their gender.
2. There is significant difference in academic motivation of secondary school students with respect to their location.
3. There is significant difference in academic motivation of secondary school students with respect the type of school.

Conclusion

The above analysis clarifies that significant difference exists amid academic motivation of Secondary school students. Academic motivation of Secondary school students is notably and positively related with their academic achievement. It is advisable for schools to teach

and motivate their Secondary school students during their scholastic and co-scholastic periods and instructions. The Ministry of School Education should also carry out motivational events and talk shows especially for Secondary school students. Parents also must show interest as it is an important part in motivating the school students regularly and consistently. School Heads must always practice sensible and well organised strategies in order to motivate their Secondary school students in both scholastic, co-scholastic activities to improve their overall academic growth.

Limitation of the Study

1. The sample is delimited to 60 students of secondary school students.
2. The sample is delimited to a secondary school of the district Haridwar, Uttarakhand.
3. The study is delimited to some demographic variables viz. Gender, Locality and type of school.

Educational Implications

1. The study will be helpful for the teachers in understanding the level of growth and development when it comes Academic Motivation among their students for a bright future.
2. The study will be helpful to the school administration also while they develop the co-scholastic activities for building the academic motivation of the students for better overall growth and development.

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